

A Two-Phase Approach for the Electrical Layout Optimization of the Offshore Wind Farms

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Abstract—Due to the current focus on offshore renewable energies worldwide, more capacity of them is expected in the future. The electrical layout design considerably affects overall implementation cost of these offshore power plants as well as the losses of energy inside the farms. Considering the increasing size of offshore wind farms, it is necessary to develop more robust and computationally efficient methods to design the electrical layout of these farms. In this work, a two-phase approach is proposed for the optimization of the electrical layout of the offshore wind farms; the proposed framework aims at the minimization of the ohmic losses and the cost of the cables. To solve the optimization problem, Simulated Annealing (SA) is applied in this study. A tool is also developed using Python programming language to implement the framework for the optimization of the electrical layout of the offshore farms. The proposed method is then applied to a farm with 100 turbines and an overall rated capacity of 1GW. The results approved the accuracy of the two-phase approach in finding the optimal electrical layout as well as the high efficiency in terms of the computational burden.

Keywords—Offshore wind farm, electrical layout, optimization, simulated annealing.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the early years of the 20th century, offshore farms were constructed in The UK, Denmark, Sweden, and The Netherlands in the ranges of 40-100 MW; one of the objectives of these farms, besides providing power to the grid, was to test the technology and make incremental improvements on it [1]. Currently, larger projects in the range of thousands of Megawatts are being explored [2]. Considering the energy transition policies, the continuous construction of these large Renewable Energy Sources (RES) is crucial to guarantee more sustainable human activities [2], [3], [4].

Cost reduction and operational efficiency improvement are among the main objectives in the design and operation of the large Offshore Wind Farm (OWF) [5]. OWFs are more complex systems with increased costs of construction and operations at sea when compared to onshore installations. This indicates the importance of the accuracy of the optimization strategies applied for the design of the electrical layout of these systems [6]. Such an optimization strategy aims at connecting all the devices within the farm, and with the shore considering the constraint on the available equipment, physical limitations of construction, cost limits, and the rules of safety and operation that should be met [7].

With greater offshore farms in the future, the losses will be more critical [7]. Furthermore, the cost of the equipment and cables, especially for offshore installations, is quite elevated [6], [8]. These factors contribute to a need for optimization strategies aiming at layout design and equipment selection. However, with the increasing interest in larger

offshore RES projects, efficient methods are needed to optimize the electrical layout of the farms in a computationally efficient framework.

There are several optimization approaches applied in the literature to solve the optimization problem for the electrical layout design of offshore farms. This includes a variety of mathematical and meta-heuristic methods like the Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) in [5], Mixed Integer Quadratically Constrained Program (MIQCP) in [9], Genetic Algorithm in [6], [10], and Particle Swarm Optimization in [3]. Considering the high computational burden, it has taken a considerable time in all of the above-mentioned methods to find the optimal solution.

In the implemented optimization methods, whether the mathematical or meta-heuristic ones, the optimization includes a simultaneous study of the layout design as well as the sizing of the cables. This in theory should be the most accurate approach to perform the optimization, and compare fully designed grids with each other. However, the optimization process can be done in a 2-phase approach in which initially the layout optimization is performed, and in the second phase, the cable sizing is implemented. This can decrease the computational burden and increase the efficiency of the optimization method.

In this paper, a novel electrical layout design method for offshore farms is proposed which is composed of two optimization phases. Accordingly, in the first phase, the layout structure of the farm is optimized while the sizing of the cables is implemented in the second phase. Splitting the electrical layout design and the cable sizing, the proposed method aims to decrease the calculation burden of the optimization study. [11]. However, this electrical layout optimization method, including the two phases, is designed to minimize the losses and the investment costs [12].

The paper is structured as follows; Section I contains the introduction, literature review, motivation, and main contributions. Section II consists of the Mathematical Model implemented. Section III includes the Solution Strategy adopted. In Section IV the five studied cases are presented. In Section V, the Results and Discussion are provided. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section VI.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

In this Section, the mathematical model of the optimization problem is presented. The descriptions given in the following subsections include the calculation of the losses, costs of the components, objective functions, constraints, and the model applied for the calculation of renewable energy generation.

A. Objective function

The objective function of the optimization study is given in (1) which encompasses the Total Cost of the Farm (TCF), for a period of 25 years as the horizon of the project, considering 8760 hours per year [9], [13].

$$\min TCF = C_{inv} + \sum_{y=1}^{25} \frac{1}{(1+r)^y} \sum_{d=1}^{365} \sum_{h=1}^{24} C_{loss} \quad (1)$$

where C_{inv} is the investment cost, r is the average expected interest rate including inflation, y is the index of the year, and C_{loss} is the cost of the energy losses in the power lines that are calculated using (2).

$$C_{loss} = UC_{EL} * E_{loss} \quad (2)$$

where UC_{EL} is the price of energy that is 50 €/MWh in this study, and E_{loss} is the energy loss in MWh.

B. Costs of the different components

The costs of cable connectors and other equipment necessary to establish connections between the nodes in the farm are simplified in this study and a cost model based on the cross-section of the cable is used. Altogether, based on [8], the cost of the connections is calculated using (3) [k€/km]:

$$Cost_{AC} = \alpha + \beta e^{\frac{\gamma * I_n}{10^5}} \quad (3)$$

where I_n represents cable ampacity [A], while α , β , γ , are the coefficients for the nominal voltage. For the case of 132kV, the values for the cost parameters are given in Table 1 [8]. The cables considered in this study are the single core copper XLPE insulated that the respective nominal currents, nominal apparent power, and costs are given in Table 2 [14].

Table 1. The values for α , β and γ for a 132 kV cable

α [k€/km]	β [k€/km]	γ [k€/km]
249.72	26.48	379.50

Table 2. Cost of the cables applied in the study

Cross section (mm^2)	Nominal current (A)	Nominal apparent power S_n (MVA)	Cost (k€/km)
240	670	153	585.2
300	750	171.5	704.0
400	845	193.2	901.0
500	950	217.2	1219.3
630	1065	243.5	1749.0
1000	1290	294.9	3767.0

C. Wind power calculation

In this study, Vestas V164-10 MW offshore wind turbine is applied to model the wind energy generation in the farm using (4) [15].

$$P_h = \frac{1}{2} * \rho * A * v_h^3 * c_p \quad (4)$$

where P_h is power output of the WT for the wind speed in hour h of the study, ρ is the air density, A is the blade area, V_h is the wind speed in hour h , c_p is the power coefficient of the wind turbine.

III. SOLUTION STRATEGY

In this paper, a 2-phase strategy is proposed to solve the optimization problem defined for the design of the electrical system of offshore wind farms. In this section, after primary descriptions of the rules applied for finding the optimal electrical layout of the farm using the proposed 2-phase method, the different steps towards implementation of this strategy are described. Furthermore, an alternative 1-phase method is also defined to provide the base results for the evaluation of the 2-phase method. It should be emphasized that in both solution strategies, Simulated Annealing (SA) is applied to solve the optimization problem; the descriptions of the implementation of this optimization algorithm are also given in this section.

A. Rules of Engagement

For the design of the electrical layout in this study, there are specific rules that should be met during the optimization; these rules are named Rules of Engagement (RE) and are as follows:

- All nodes must be directly or indirectly (via other nodes) connected to the node of connection to the mainland (i.e. the node where the substation is located).
- The maximum number of connections must be the number of nodes minus one; the objective, in this case, is to avoid closed-ring connections.
- The available directions of connection are only to adjacent nodes; this rule aims at preventing crossing lines.
- There is no limit assigned to the number of connections that a node can have.

B. The seed grid

To efficiently perform the optimization study using SA, a seed grid is required at the starting point of the solution strategy. The seed topology applied in this optimization study for size10 grid (10×10 turbines in the farm) is displayed in Figure 1 it is a common electrical layout for smaller installations. This is a crucial step in the making of the optimization algorithm, since starting with a random grid proved to make the execution of the program much slower and can have a considerable effect on the optimality of the results. It should be noted that all the other seed grids for the other sizes of the farm fall under a similar topology, in which the bottom common connection lines for all the columns correspond to the side of the grid that is facing directly to the shore.

Figure 1: representation of the WT locations and seed grid

C. The proposed two-phase method

As described, the 2-Phase approach is developed to find the electrical layout of the connections and the size of the cables in two separate phases. Hence, in this method, after obtaining the optimal electrical layout using SA, the cable optimization is performed in the next phase. It should be noted that the possibility of installing parallel cables for the same line is also considered and applied in this study. This method is applied in 6 Steps that are shown in Figure 1 and are described in the following sections.

Figure 2: Steps of the optimization 2-phase algorithm

1) STEP 1: Formation of the seed grid

In this step, the seed grid is formed based on the description given in Figure 1.

2) STEP 2: Evaluation of the seed grid

In this step, the evaluation of the seed grid is performed to obtain the power flow values to generate the initial cost of the losses to be compared with the other generated grids by the SA.

3) STEP 3: Optimization using SA

SA is applied to solve the optimization problem in this step. Some descriptions of the implementation of SA are given in the following paragraphs.

- The values of the temperature and best cost are initialized. The initial best cost is the value obtained in Step 2.
- The new neighbor grid is generated using a function that randomly selects a new adjacent node and makes that connection; to maintain the limit of connections, a search is made to detect closed rings. The closed ring is then opened in the line with the lowest power flow.

- Since there is always a chance of having disconnected nodes or groups of disconnected nodes, another search is made to ensure that the remaining disconnected nodes are reconnected.
- This modified grid is evaluated from the point of view of the losses. If the loss is lower than the previous “best”, it is replaced with the new one.
- When the temperature reaches a value below the minimum temperature that is set, STEP 3 is completed.

4) STEP 4

In this step, the final layout is obtained. A power flow is performed, and the values of the losses are compared to the initial grid.

5) STEP 5

In this step, the cables are selected considering the power flow results of Step 4. Accordingly, the cable optimization algorithm is applied not only to assess all the available cables but also to determine whether parallel cables should be selected or not.

6) STEP 6

Finally, in STEP 6, the results are shown graphically, and a description is provided on each line connection.

D. The alternative 1-phase method

To evaluate the proposed two-phase method, an alternative 1-phase strategy is also applied in this study for electrical layout optimization. In this method, the grid layout optimization and cable sizing with respect to cross sections, ampacity, cost, resistance, and reactance, are implemented simultaneously.

This method is applied in 5 Steps that are shown in Figure 13 and are described in the following sections.

Figure 3: Steps of the optimization of the 1-phase algorithm

1) *STEP 1: Formation of the seed grid*

In this step, the seed grid is formed based on the description given for 1.

2) *STEP 2: Evaluation of the seed grid*

In this step, the evaluation of the seed grid is performed to obtain the power flow values to generate the initial cost of the losses to be compared with the other generated grids by the SA.

3) *STEP 3: Optimization using SA*

SA is applied to solve the optimization problem in this step. Some descriptions of the implementation of SA are given in the following paragraphs.

- The values of the temperature and best cost are initialized. The initial best cost is the value obtained in Step 2.
- The new neighbor grid is generated using a function that randomly selects a new adjacent node and makes that connection; to maintain the limit of connections, a search is made to detect closed rings. The closed ring is then opened in the line with the lowest power flow.
- Since there is always a chance of having disconnected nodes or groups of disconnected nodes, another search is made to ensure that the remaining disconnected nodes are reconnected.
- In this step, the cables are selected considering the power flow results. Accordingly, the cable optimization algorithm is applied not only to assess all the available cables but also to determine whether parallel cables should be selected or not.
- This modified grid is evaluated from the point of view of the losses and cost of the cables. If the total cost is lower than the previous “best”, it is replaced with the new one.
- When the temperature reaches a value below the minimum temperature that is set, STEP 3 is completed.

4) *STEP 4*

In this step, the final layout is obtained. A power flow is performed, and the values of the losses are compared to the initial grid.

5) *STEP 5*

Finally, in STEP 5, the results are shown graphically, and a description is provided on each line connection.

E. Simulated Annealing (SA)

Simulated Annealing (SA) is a meta-heuristic method widely used to determine optimization studies [11]. The SA is a derivative-free optimization method that is based on the process of heating a solid until its melting point, which is then followed by a slow cooling process by decreasing the ambient temperature [16]. As described, this meta-heuristic method is the basis for the optimization of the electrical layout of the farm in this paper. One of the main advantages of the SA process is the low probability of getting stuck in a local minima, and usually achieving the global optimal or suboptimal solution [17]. Considering the high number of possible connections in the grid, especially in cases with a high number of turbines, SA is applied in this study to avoid local minimum, thus being more likely to reach a global optimum point. It should be noted that the same parameters of SA such as initial temperature and cooling rate have been

applied in both 1-Phase and 2-Phase algorithms. However, the applied cooling rate is not constant and adaptively changes based on (5) and (6).

$$T_{i+1} = T_i \times (0.5 + 0.5 \times \alpha) \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha = 1 - i/M \quad (6)$$

where, T_i is the temperature in the iteration i of the optimization, and M is the maximum number of iterations.

The change in the temperature for the studied problem in the Size10 grid with an initial temperature of 5000 is demonstrated in Figure 4. As presented in 4, in the early stages of the optimization, the algorithm can analyze a larger spectrum of electrical layout possibilities. This initial analysis of a wider range of candidates also decreases the probability of getting stuck in local minimums compared to a fixed cooling rate.

Figure 4: Temperature variation for grid size10 with a dynamic cooling rate

It should be emphasized that a repair operation of some results coming from the SA is implemented in this study in which for the cases where nodes are left unconnected or where closed rings are created, an operator similar to the one applied in [18], [19], [20] is used to transform unfeasible grids into feasible candidates. This process avoids the removal of potentially acceptable solutions due to the infeasibility while they can be corrected with slight modifications. This way, a higher level of flexibility in applying the different values of search operators can also be provided for the optimizer.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the proposed method for the electrical layout design of offshore wind farms is examined in sample farms and the results are discussed; accordingly, five case studies were applied to compare the performance of the 1-Phase and the 2-Phase algorithms.

As given in the formulations, the simulations are implemented over a year considering 1-hour time steps. The wind speed data of 2019 is applied in this study that is taken from the Copernicus dataset from the offshore northern region of Portugal. Considering each MWh loss of energy one less MWh to be sold, a 50 €/MWh value for the cost of the loss is considered based on the average price in the years before 2020 in the Iberian electricity market (MIBEL) [21]. Finally, it

should be noted that an interest rate of 4% is considered for the economic assessments of this study.

To conduct these simulations, a tool is developed using Python programming language for both 1-Phase and 2-Phase methods. For all power flow calculations, the PandaPower tool [22] is used to ensure the high accuracy of results while also being validated by PowerWorld and PSSE. All the simulations were made on a desktop with a Ryzen 9 5900X 24-core CPU.

A. Case studies

The cases for this study are sample farms with 9, 16, 25, 49, and 100 WT as given in Table 3. Each WT has a rated power of 10MW. The distance defined for the wind turbines is 1km for each side.

Table 3: The five case studies, grid sizes, and total rated power of the farms

Case name	Number of WTs	Grid size	Total MW
Size3	9	3 by 3	90
Size4	16	4 by 4	160
Size5	25	5 by 5	250
Size7	49	7 by 7	490
Size10	100	10 by 10	1000

These cases have been selected to examine the effectiveness of the methods on a range of different grid sizes. It should be noted that these case studies are identically applied in 1-phase and 2-phase approaches.

B. Results and discussions

The simulations are implemented in the specified grids, and the results are given and discussed in this section. It should be noted that in this paper, the optimization is performed several times to increase the accuracy of the results. Accordingly, for both 1-Phase and 2-Phase methods, ten optimizations are performed for each case. The results presented in this paper reflect the best outcomes among the whole implementations of the optimizations for each case.

In all the cases studied, the most central point of the farm is selected to connect the floating substation and the onshore one. An example of the best layout solution for grid Size10 is displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Optimized layout for grid Size 10

The final prices of both 1-Phase and 2-Phase algorithms of each respective optimized grid, considering the costs of the losses over 25 years are displayed in Figure 6. It is clear that in smaller grids, up to Size5 (25 WT), the total cost is similar in the two algorithms. However, for the larger grids, especially

in Size10 (100 WT) the 1-Phase strategy displays a higher total cost (120.37 million Euros); in other words, the grids designed in the 1-phase method require bigger and much more expensive cables to cope with the larger values of current in the lines.

Figure 6: Total Cost Function in Millions of Euros

It is also vital to analyze how 1-Phase and 2-Phase cases affect the losses. Accordingly, the loss reduction comparing the seed grid described in Section III over the 25 years of the study is given in Table 4. According to the results, using the 2-phase method, the loss cost reduction is over 30% with an increase to 47% in the largest grid. However, the accuracy of results considerably decreases in the 1-Phase method from the size7 grid, and it results in the worst value in the size10 grid. However, even in the smaller grids, from size 3 to size7, the 2-Phase strategy provides better solutions.

Table 4: Reduction in losses cost over the 25 years

	Reduction 1-Phase	Reduction 2-Phase
Size3	33.51%	39.24%
Size4	35.70%	37.65%
Size5	33.56%	35.33%
Size7	11.15%	32.19%
Size10	2.53%	46.81%

The execution time of optimization in seconds for both 1-phase and 2-phase methods is given for the different farm sizes in Table 5. According to the results, it is clear that the 2-phase algorithm is much faster than the 1-phase. Since the grid size increases exponentially (quadratically), the time of optimization follows the same trend. Hence, for the grid size above 5, the 1-phase system becomes almost impractical due to both the time of the implementation and the accuracy of results. Relative change of the simulation time considering the increase of the size is also provided in Figure 6.

Table 5: Execution times in seconds for both algorithms for the different grid sizes

Grid size	1-Phase (T1)	2-Phase (T2)	T2/T1
Size3	3149.67	68.3468	46.08
Size4	5616.50	83.3901	67.35
Size5	14467.11	117.4329	123.19
Size7	59407.62	344.9208	172.24
Size10	290593.66	1395.218	208.28

For both 1-Phase and 2-Phase algorithms, ten optimizations for each case were performed. The optimization is performed 10 times to increase the accuracy of the solution.

From the different tests conducted, the results did not alter much. However, the accuracy of the results improved 1-2%

The growth of the execution times for both algorithms is shown in Figure 7. The 2-phase algorithm has a lower rate of increase in simulation times as the grid sizes increase.

Figure 7: Execution time increases between grids sizes.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a novel 2-phase approach is proposed for the optimization of the electrical layout of offshore farms. In the first phase of the method, the layout of the farm is structured while in the second, the cables are sized. This optimization method aims at minimizing long-term electrical losses and initial investment costs. To validate this new method, it is compared with the conventional 1-Phase method in which the sizing of the cables and the designing of the farm are done simultaneously. According to the results, the 2-phase method can considerably decrease the computational burden, increase the accuracy of the results, and decrease the implementation time of the study compared to the 1-phase method. According to the results, the advantage of the two-phase method over the 1-Phase is considerable in larger farms; hence, this method can be a very important alternative for the conventional 1-phase method in the optimization of large offshore parks.

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